

DEMONSTRATING KNOWLEDGE OF THE IMPORTANCE OF GRADED LANGUAGE IN THE CLASSROOM. DEDUCTIVE AND INDUCTIVE METHOD

Makhliyo Diyorova

Assistant teacher of the Faculty of Foreign languages of Karshi engineering and economics institute

Annotation: The article demonstrating knowledge of the importance of graded language in the classroom: deductive and inductive method provides information about pedagogical methods.

Keywords: strategy, concepts, casual, extent, theory, assertion ,premises, deductive

Deductive approach involves drawing inferences from premises or assertions. The deductive method centers on the theory. According to this strategy , the classroom is mostly occupied by teachers. This strategy is regarded as a teacher-centered approach. The instructor describes the grammar rule. Aftercomprehending the grammatical rule, students begin completing tasks relating to the topic. This method makes it simple to explain casual linkages between concepts and variables, quantify concepts, and generalize research findings to some extent.

Weakness: Because of all classes are centered on theory , students may find them more tedious. If lessons are dull , students become less engaged

Inductive

Strength:

In this method,teachers begin the course with contextualized examples and language tips explanations. The instructor requires active engagement in the classroom through teaching and questioning, and students attempt to discover grammar rules on their own. Students develop grammar principles by studying the recurring important elements in the supplied sentences. This strategy incorporates the active engagements of all student levels in the classroom. The advantages of the inductive method are; student-centered orientation. It provides a deeper comprehension. This method places greater responsibility on the students to find grammar rules

Weakness; The limitation of the inductive method: This is a time –consuming procedure. For students with a lower reading level, drawing conclusions about the topic can be quite challenging.

The Communicative Approach

Strength:

Pupil who have communication needs are more likely to ask questions. The pupils can use the acquired language as a means of communication. It is more humanistic since it involves the students, actions in real – world circumstances, and has meaning in terms of language functions. In the classroom, learners have more possibilities to exhibit their personality when they engage in communicative interactions.

Weakness;

The teacher must devote more time to preparation. It need the teacher’s inventiveness to bring life to the classroom. The instructor should be able to use their knowledge of the content in a variety of realistic classroom circumstances. Because they are shy in front of their classmates, shy students should be discouraged from producing phrases that reflect their ideas.

B. Examples of graded language:

I) elementary level:

Your instructor requested that you view the images . Then , attempt to compose a tale using the images below. Use present simple and present continuous while composing a narrative. When describing the persons in the photographs, you must focus on their appearance and attire. They facilitate the construction of present continuous phrases.

II) intermediate level:

You teacher has asked you to create a short story. Examine the images below and compose a narrative using past continuous and past perfect tenses. When writing a story, the first step is to establish the setting. To accomplish this, you must believe that you are viewing the images and attempt to explain the setting , time,weather, participants and their emotions. You can employ your senses to create a more vivid description. Thus, you are able to articulate what you see,hear,feel, and smell.

III) advanced level:

You are required to compose a narrative using the images beneath your teacher.Never begin a narrative composition without first determining the plot. Use time phrases such as before, until, then, finally, to clarify the order of occurances.

Use direct and reported speech to create a vivid narrative. Use a variety of adjectives and adverbs to emphasize emotions and activities. This will add interest to your article.

The benefits of using graded languages:

Grading language makes students feel more comfortable in class. Because a teacher assesses linguistic instructions, based on the student's proficiency level, students are able to understand their tasks. It helps pupils communicate with tasks. Students observe the instructor. Students develop respect and accountability.

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